

HISTORICAL VIEWS OF ABU RAIKHAN BERUNI

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Abstract. *In this article, it is written that similar discoveries, scientific works, and samples created by the scientific genius of Abu Rayhan Beruni testify to his rich legacy.*

Key words: *scientific works, heritage, manuscript, creativity, history, philosophy, thinker.*

ИСТОРИЧЕСКИЕ ВИДЫ АБУ РАЙХАНА БЕРУНИ

Аннотация. *В данной статье написано, что подобные открытия, научные труды и образцы, созданные научным гением Абу Райхана Беруни, свидетельствуют о его богатом наследии.*

Ключевые слова: *научные труды, наследие, рукопись, творчество, история, философия, мыслитель.*

It is difficult to give a full assessment of the discoveries created by the scientific genius of the great encyclopedist Abu Rayhan Beruni. Despite the fact that only 31 of Beruni's more than 150 scientific works have come down to us, these incomplete examples of scholarly manuscripts testify to his rich legacy. Abu Rayhan Muhammad ibn al-Biruni was born in the year 362 Hijri, 973 AD, in the city of Qiyat, the center of ancient Khorezm. Although Beruni knows many languages, he mainly wrote in Arabic. He became a scholar under Khorezmshah ibn Ma'mun. He created a number of works related to history, astronomy, mineralogy, philosophy ("Geodesy", "Mineralogy", "Relics from past generations", "India", etc.). Beruni was one of the first in world science to propose unique new ideas about the theory of seas and the creation of a spherical globe of the Earth, calculated the radius of the Earth, explained the state of vacuum, i.e. space, 500 years before the voyage of Columbus, he proposed the view that there is a continent behind the Pacific and Atlantic oceans. surdi, developed the theory of mineral classification and their occurrence, founded the science of geodesy. That is why it is not for nothing that the 11th century is called "Beruni's century" by historians of natural sciences all over the world. Emphasizing that the necessary work has been done to build a new state and society in our country during the years of independence, special attention is paid to the study of the scientific heritage of the encyclopedist scientist Abu Raikhan Beruni, who was known to the world during the years of independence in our republic, as he said, "Our ancient history, rich cultural heritage, national religious values, and identity have been restored" [1]. attention was drawn. On August 25, 2022, the Presidential Decree

No. PQ-361 "On the wide celebration of the 1050th anniversary of the birth of the great thinker and encyclopedist Abu Rayhan Beruni on an international and republican scale" was adopted. Beruni Khorezmshah worked in the "Ma'mun Academy", one of the largest scientific centers of his time, which was established in Urganch under the leadership of Ma'mun. Later, due to various reasons, he was forced to go to the city of Ghazna. Abu Raykhan Beruni's contribution to the sciences of the Middle Ages, especially astronomy, physics, mathematics, geodesy, geography, geology, the history of sciences, and other sciences, made him known to the world. embodied the ideas Beruni was one of the founders of science based on experience in Central Asia, the Near and Middle East. He emphasized the importance of logical conclusions and comparisons in understanding natural phenomena. The philosopher was also able to show the process of transition from emotional knowledge to mental knowledge. He pointed out the objective and subjective reasons for the creation of knowledge in man and opposed mixing scientific problems with religious issues. Beruni attached great importance to the role of experience in knowledge, he put forward the idea that experience is a criterion for checking the correctness of our knowledge. Beruni's philosophical thinking focused on problems such as substance, space, time, lawfulness, necessity, chance, movement and development in his views on existence. He acknowledges the creation of existence by God. According to him, there is a possibility that the heavenly bodies of the universe were scattered at the time of God's creation, and then moved and gathered at a certain point.

He developed and developed new methods of scientific knowledge - methods of experience and experimentation. Therefore, his outlook is anti-scholastic in nature. Nature - includes the whole world, where natural and material phenomena are subject to certain laws. Nature, he explains, is something that determines the legal processes that have natural power. He condemns the explanation of nature through miracles. Because he put forward the opinion that there are no miracles in nature, and if they do happen, they must happen through reason. God only played the role of the first impulse. Nature, the whole celestial sphere moves by itself. He concludes that "if there is no beginning of movement, the existence of any mover is doubtful." According to him, matter is eternal. "There is no doubt that natural power finds matter and does not lose it." Beruni's theory of knowledge is full of materialistic rules. The source of human knowledge about the world is emotional knowledge. Without senses, a person cannot know anything. Beruni's historical research is the basis for philosophical and logical conclusions through mathematics, calculations, measurements, laws of nature and the universe, geometric precisions. Beruni in his works. He revealed a unique way of the world of thought of the East. He gave clear ideas about the history

of mankind, its emergence, development and crisis. He created a school of scientific study of the creation of the world and the universe, the emergence of man, the stages of development of nations, historical events, natural phenomena and their meaning. Beruni's philosophical understanding of history strongly rejects the first primitive views about the origin of man, his body structure and different languages, faces, facial features and body structure, color. and examines views from the perspective of secular science. Beruni speaks many languages. At first, he studied Arabic, which was considered a scientific language in the Muslim world at that time, and Persian, Syriac, Greek-Greek, and Sanskrit languages. Later, after mastering this language, he translates scientific works from it into Arabic and from Arabic into Sanskrit. Only some of these works have reached our time. Beruni's words in his work "Memorials from ancient peoples" that "I narrate their words that have reached me. I try to correct the broken ones as much as I can, cancel the lies, and find out the truth" indicate that he is a selfless person who loves the truth in science. While he works on historical sources, he does not treat each source as absolute truth. He seeks the truth from within the truth and in this way seeks to restore the truth of history. Beruni's philosophical heritage is of great importance in educating the youth of our independent country in the spirit of patriotism, humane attitude to work and faith.

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